

Molecular Interaction and Antidiabetic Potential of Indian Heliotrope (*heliotropium indicum*) Leaf Extract: Inhibition of Human Salivary α -amylase and Antioxidant Profiling"

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Abstract

Indian heliotrope (IH) or Indian turnsole is a natural medicinal plant from the Boraginaceae family, with numerous medicinal properties. The molecular interaction of its ethanolic leaf extract with the diabetes-linked enzyme, human salivary α -amylase (HSAmy), was investigated using multi-spectroscopic approaches under simulated salivary condition pH 6.8. The antidiabetic activity of IH extract was assessed by HSAmy inhibition assay, and its antioxidant properties were examined by DPPH and ABTS assays. Phytochemical screening and HPLC analysis were also conducted. The phytochemical screening and HPLC analysis revealed the presence of key phytochemicals as and major bioactive compounds. The extract showed concentration dependent inhibition of HSAmy invitro, demonstrating its ability to slow down the digestion and absorption of carbohydrates. The extract demonstrated significant antioxidant properties as depicted by DPPH and ABTS activities. The fluorescence quenching showed that IH quenches the intrinsic fluorescence of HSAmy through a mixed quenching mechanism, with a red shift in emission spectra, accompanied by hydrophobic interaction and endothermic process that was spontaneous in nature. IH exhibited mixed-type inhibition of the enzyme, with an inhibition constant (K_i) of 28.37 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and an apparent coefficient (α) of 0.46. The enzyme structural conformation was compromised, indicating alterations in the hydrogen bonding pattern of the polypeptide backbone and HSAmy secondary structure. Indian heliotrope shows strong α -amylase inhibition and antioxidant activity, highlighting its potential for managing postprandial hyperglycemia. These findings support further exploration of the plant as a natural antidiabetic agent.

Keywords: Indian heliotrope (IH); Human salivary α -amylase (HSAmy); Fluorescence Quenching; Antidiabetic; Antioxidant; Phytochemicals

INTRODUCTION

Human salivary-amylase (HSAmy) is a type of endoenzyme that is mainly released by the salivary glands and is involved in breaking down internal α 1, 4 glycosidic bonds in starch molecule. The resultant reaction forms smaller oligosaccharides, maltose and dextrans (Visvanathan *et al.*, 2020). HSAmy is very important in the digestion of carbohydrates in the mouth which significantly

controls the rate of glucose release and uptake. Therefore, it directly affects the postprandial blood glucose, which explains why it can be used to regulate glycemic response (Falese *et al.*, 2021).

The inhibition of the α -amylase activity has been reported as one of the potential strategies in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) because it reduces the rate of carbohydrate hydrolysis and slows glucose absorption. Pharmacological interventions of α -amylase inhibition include the use of acarbose and miglitol. Nevertheless, their therapeutic use is usually restricted by the negative gastrointestinal adverse effects, such as flatulence, diarrhea, and abdominal discomfort (Padhi *et al.*, 2020; Khursheed *et al.*, 2019). Such constraints have led to the quest of safer, natural α -amylase inhibitors that are found in medicinal plants.

Indian heliotrope (IH) (*Heliotropium indicum*) is one of the promising plants that contain various phytochemicals and has a broad ethnomedicinal application. It has traditionally been used in wound, inflammatory and microbial infection treatment, and a number of studies have indicated the occurrence of bioactive compounds with antioxidant and enzyme-inhibitory properties (Pahuja *et al.*, 2022). Despite the long history of traditional use of *Heliotropium indicum* in the management of diabetes in different cultures, there is still less scientific evidence that specifically explores the influence of this compound on human salivary α -amylase. The majority of the literature available on it has concentrated on its antioxidant or antimicrobial properties and has not understood the mechanism by which it may act as an antidiabetic by inhibiting digestive enzymes.

Considering the current increase in the prevalence of type 2 diabetes worldwide and the necessity of safer and cheaper methods of treatment, it is high-time and necessary to study the binding interaction between the extracts of *Heliotropium indicum* and HSAmy. This means that the identification of natural, cost effective and non-toxic α -amylase inhibitors may result in designing functional food ingredients or supplementary curative substances that can be utilized in the management of glycemia index. Moreover, the antioxidant action of *H. indicum* can also offer some protective effects on pancreatic cells and alleviate oxidative stress which turns out to be an unavoidable result of hyperglycemia.

Thus, the current research will assess the inhibitory capacity of the *H. indicum* extract with HSAmy, clarify the underlying (potentially antioxidant-dependent) mechanisms and describe the enzyme extract interactions by using spectroscopic methods. This study will offer scientific explanation of the *H. indicum* traditional application in managing diabetes, and it may be used in the coming years to identify the exact phytochemical components that induce HSAmy inhibition, which will lead to the realization of future pharmacological and nutraceutical development.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The spectroscopic grade organic solvents, HSAmy (molecular weight, 62000 g/mol). Commercial analytical grade preparations reagents: DPPH (1,1 diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) and ABTS (2'-azino-bis 3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich Fine Chemicals in St. Louis, Missouri, USA. Bio-Rad, based in Palo Alto, California, produced the BSA standard and Bradford reagent kit. Every other chemical was a reagent/analytical grade commercial product. Protein concentrations of HSAmy was assessed using the Bradford technique (1976).

Equipment used

A Hitachi F-4500 spectrophotometer (Tokyo, Japan) with a 10 mm quartz cell and a 150W xenon lamp, Shimadzu double beam UV–Visible spectrophotometer (UV-1800) equipped with a 1.0 cm quartz cells

Sample Collection and Treatment

Indian heliotrope (IH) leaves were obtained from Olorunsogo, Oke-Osun area, in Ado Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria, Lat: 7.6233° N; Long: 5.2209° E. The leaves were washed, and air dried to a constant weight at room temperature 25-27 °C for 9 days. The dried leaves were pulverized into fine powder and stored for further use. All reagents and buffers used were filtered through a 0.45 Minisart Syringe filter.

Sample Extraction

The extraction was done explicitly, as described by Revathy *et al.* (2011). Briefly, 42 g of IH leaves powder was extracted with 250 ml of ethanol and stirred for 48 h. The extracts were purified, concentrated using a rotating vacuum evaporator at 40 °C under reduced pressure to give 4.3 g, an extraction yield of 10.24 % and then stored at 4 °C until use.

$$\text{Extraction Yield (\%)} = (4.3 \text{ g} / 42 \text{ g}) \times 100 = 10.24 \%$$

Phytochemicals Screening and Antioxidant Analysis of the Extract

The method described by Edeoga (2005) was used to conduct the qualitative and quantitative phytochemical analysis of the leaf extract regarding the presence of alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, tannins, steroids, terpenoid, and others. The DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging activity was determined by the method of Braca *et al.* (2001). We have taken 0.004% (101.5 µM) of DPPH solution and incubated it for 30 min and the absorbance was read at 520 nm. The IH leaf extract ABTS radical scavenging activity was measured as explained by Braca *et al.* (2001). A 7 mM ABTS solution was made and following 15 min incubation at 30 °C with reaction mixtures, absorbance was read at 734 nm.

HSAmy Inhibition Assay

The technique developed by Alqahtani *et al.* (2019) was used for the HSAmy inhibition assay. Briefly, different concentrations of ethanol stocked extract of IH (20, 40, 60 and 80 µg/ml) were produced in ethanol. A mixture of 40 µL from the various concentrations of IH plant extract and 20 µL of HSAmy (1.83 µM) was combined with 1 mL of Potassium-phosphate buffer (25 mM, pH 6.8) and incubated at 37 °C for 10 min. The reaction was then started by adding 50 µL of 5 mM starch to the solutions. After 60 minutes of incubation at 37 °C, the reaction mixtures were stopped by adding 300 µL of 0.1 M DNSA. The absorbance (Abs) at 400 nm was used to calculate the α-amylase activity. The mean values were obtained from triplicate experiments. Equation (1) was used to calculate the percentage of HSAmy activity that was inhibited.

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Abs}_{\text{Control}} - \text{Abs}_{\text{Extract}}}{\text{Abs}_{\text{Control}}} \right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The inhibition kinetic mechanism was deduced by equation 2

$$\frac{1}{V} = \frac{K_M}{V_{\max}} \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{K_i} \right) \frac{1}{[S]} + \frac{1}{V_{\max}} \left(1 + \frac{[I]}{\alpha K_i} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where the relative parameters of the extract binding to HSAm_y are the reaction rate (V_o), reaction rate constant (K_M), maximum reaction velocity (V_{max}), and inhibition constant (K_i). The inhibitor concentration, substrate concentration and apparent coefficient concentrations are denoted by [I], [S] and ‘ α ’ respectively.

Fluorescence Quenching Measurements

A Hitachi F-4500 spectrophotometer (Tokyo, Japan) with a 10 mm quartz cell and a 150W xenon lamp was used to measure the fluorescence spectra. The fluorescence spectrophotometer (made by Pharmacia Biotech) was fitted with a chilled water bath and connected to a Windows XP computer, from which the Hitachi FL solution software managed the entire setup.

The response time was 0.01sec. A 2.0 mL solution of HSAm_y (1.83 μ M) in a 25 mM Potassium-phosphate buffer solution with a pH of 6.8 was put to a 1.0 cm quartz cuvette and then titrated manually by successive addition of ethanol stock solution of IH to a final concentration of 22.5 μ g/ml. Temperatures between 288 and 313 K were used to measure the fluorescence spectra.

The emission wavelengths were scanned from 300 to 500 nm, with the excitation wavelength fixed at 280 nm. Equation (3) was used to adjust each fluorescence spectrum of HSAm_y for any potential inner filter impact when it was exposed to various concentrations of IH

$$F_c = F_m e^{(A_1+A_2)/2} \quad (3)$$

Where F_c and F_m are the corrected and measured fluorescence respectively, A_1 and A_2 = absorbance of IH solution at excitation and emission wavelengths respectively.

The analysis of the operative quenching mechanism was done using the mathematical model of well-known Stern-Volmer Equations, shown in (Eqn. 4 and 5) (Deng and Liu, 2012).

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + K_{SV}[Q] = 1 + K_q\tau_0[Q] \quad (4)$$

$$K_q = \frac{K_{SV}}{\tau_0} \quad (5)$$

where, F_0 and F are the fluorescence intensities of enzymes (α -glucosidase) in the absence and presence of the quencher (IH); K_{sv} is the Stern–Volmer quenching constant; [Q] is the molar concentration of quencher (IH); k_q is the bimolecular quenching rate constant; τ_0 is the average lifetime of enzymes fluorescence without the quencher ($=5.71 \times 10^{-9}$ s). The values of K_{sv} at various temperatures were established using a linear regression plot of F_0/F against [Q].

From the interactions of IH with HSAm_y, the binding constant (K_a) was determined from the reaction by using equation (6):

$$\log \frac{F_0-F}{F} = \log K_a + n \log[Q] \quad (6)$$

from the plot of the double logarithm regression plot of $\log \frac{F_0-F}{F}$ against $\log[Q]$ the values of K_a was obtained from the intercept of the plot respectively (Falese *et al.*, 2021)

The nature of binding forces and thermodynamic parameters that characterized the HSAm_y-IH complex were investigated using the van't Hoff equation (Eq. 7). From the slope and intercept of the plot of $\ln K_a$ versus $1/T$, the values of enthalpy change (ΔH) and entropy change

(ΔS) were estimated. The free energy change (ΔG) of the reaction was calculated using Equation (8).

$$\ln K_a = -\frac{\Delta H}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S}{R} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S = -RT \ln K_a \quad (8)$$

where, R is the universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) and T is absolute temperature in kelvin.

Statistical Analysis

All statistical and graphical analysis was performed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using KaleidaGraph 4.5 software (Synergy software, Reading, PA, USA) and Origin plot 8.0 software (Northampton, MA, USA). All experiments were performed in triplicate and repeated twice. Experimental data, where necessary were expressed as the mean \pm of standard deviation (S.D).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical Screening of Ethanolic Leaf Extract of IH

The results presented in Table 1 indicates that the ethanolic leaf extract of IH contains certain phytochemicals, including: saponins, tannins, terpenoids and alkaloids, present in varying amount. HPLC quantification of the phytochemical constituents present in ethanolic leaf extract of IH (Figure 1) also reveals the presence of fumaric acid, 2,4,6-trichlorophenyl tridecyl ester, 2,7-diphenyl-1,6-dioxopyridazino[4,5,2',3']pyrrolo[4',5'-d]pyridazine, 1,3,3-trimethoxy butane, 2-isobutyl-5-(2-nitro-phenyl)-[1,3,4] oxadiazole e.t.c. Recent investigations have shed light on the bioactive compounds found in natural plants, unveiling their mechanisms of interaction and highlighting their potential therapeutic applications, particularly in the development of novel drug candidates for diabetes treatment. Phytochemical analysis of the ethanolic leaf extract of IH revealed a rich profile of compounds, with saponins, alkaloids, terpenoids, tannins and flavonoids present in significant concentrations. This result corroborate the earlier findings of Pahuja *et al.* (2022) on phytochemical identification of these bioactive compounds from solvents fractions of leaves of IH extract.

Table 1: Phytochemical screening

Phytochemicals	Qualitative	Quantitative ($\mu\text{g/g}$)
Saponin	+	51.22 \pm 1.44
Alkaloid	+	44.42 \pm 0.59
Terpenoid	+	22.86 \pm 1.33
Cardiac glycoside	ND	
Flavonoid	+	6.48 \pm 0.66
Anthraquinone	ND	
Tannin	+	18.48 \pm 0.52

Key

+ = Present, ND = Not detected

Figure 1: HPLC Chromatogram of Ethanolic Leaf Extract of IH

Determination of the Radical Scavenging Activity

The result of radical scavenging activity assay in Figure 2a and 2b shows the ability of the ethanolic leaf extract of IH to scavenge against DPPH and ABTS radicals in a concentration dependent manner in relative to standard antioxidant. The potent radical scavenging activity demonstrated by IH extract, as evidenced by DPPH and ABTS, further corroborates its strong antioxidant capacity. This result conformed to the earlier report of Afroz-Shoily *et al.* (2025) who reported that plant extracts of IH demonstrated significant antioxidant and radical scavenging properties invitro and invivo. This supports the role of natural phytochemicals present in the extract as primary antioxidants, neutralizing free radicals before they can damage biological macromolecules (Kaurinovic and Vastag, 2019)

Figure 2: (a) Showing the DPPH and (b) ABTS scavenging ability of IH leaf extract. Results are expressed as Mean \pm standard deviation (n=3). Values are * ($p < 0.05$) significantly different.

Determination of HSAmy Inhibitory Property of Ethanolic Leaf Extract IH

The results in shows the ability of the extract to inhibit HSAmy at different concentration when compared with standard inhibitor acarbose. The inhibition kinetic mechanism of HSAmy by IH extract was explored intricately through the application of Lineweaver-Burk plot from eqn. 2. The visual inspection of the plot (Figure. 3a) clearly indicates the convergence of the plots outside the scope of competitive and non-competitive inhibitions. It is apparent it is a mixed type of inhibition. The Lineweaver-Burk plot was further used to determine the K_i (inhibition constant) and α (apparent coefficient) from the secondary plot of the slope against IH extract concentration (Figure 3b). The K_i and α were 28.37 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.46 respectively.

The mixed-type inhibition pattern, indicates that the extract's bioactive compounds can bind to both the free enzyme and the enzyme-substrate complex, thereby altering enzyme activity through multiple mechanisms. The mixed inhibition pattern suggests that the extract does not solely compete with the substrate for binding to the active site, but also exerts allosteric effects, potentially modifying enzyme conformation and reducing catalytic efficiency (Pesaresi, 2023). The small K_i value indicate strong inhibitory affinity of the extract for HSAmy.

Figure (3a): The Lineweaver–Burk inhibition plot of IH extract–HSAmy complex, [IH extract].0, 5.0, 10.0 and 20.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. **(3b)** secondary plot of the slope against IH extract concentration

Fluorescence Emission Spectra

Fluorescence emission spectra of HSAmy complexed with IH extract at different temperature 15-40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ is shown in Figure 4. The intrinsic aromatic fluorophore of HSAmy was used to obtain information about the interaction between HSAmy and IH extract. The fluorescence emission wavelength of HSAmy had a highest fluorescence emission peak at 343 nm in the absence of the extract when excited at 280 nm. Upon addition of concentration dependent IH

extract, there exists a notable decrease in the fluorescence intensity with a red shift (343 nm - 358 nm) in the emission spectra obtained. However, the fluorescence intensity alone showed a gradual decrease upon increasing the concentration of IH extract. These results established the interactions between IH extract and HSAm_y.

Figure 4: Fluorescence emission spectra of HSAm_y [1.83 μM] in 25 mM Potassium phosphate buffer at pH 6.8 in the presence of different concentrations of IH extract [0- 22.5μg/ml] at 25°C.

The thermodynamic parameters including; enthalpy change (ΔH), entropy change (ΔS) and free energy (ΔG°) of the reaction calculated and presented in Table 2, showed that the ΔG° values were negative at all temperature studied, with values of $\Delta S^\circ = 52.48 \text{ J.mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta H^\circ = 14.34 \text{ kJ.mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The ΔG° values from the thermodynamic parameters were found to be negative, indicating that the interaction is spontaneous at all temperatures tested (Falese *et al.*, 2021). The positive values of ΔH and ΔS imply that the complex creation was an endothermic and entropically driven process (Kolawole *et al.*, 2018).

Table 2: Binding and Thermodynamic Parameters of IH extract-HSAm_y Complex

Temp	Binding Constant (K_a)	(K_d)			
K	($\times 10^4 \text{ (Lmol}^{-1}\text{)}$)	($\times 10^{-3} \text{ (Lmol}^{-1}\text{)}$)	$\Delta H \text{ (kJmol}^{-1}\text{)}$	$\Delta S \text{ (Jmol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}\text{)}$	$\Delta G \text{ (kJmol}^{-1}\text{)}$
288	2.65	3.16			-24.38
293	2.73	3.09			-24.87
298	2.90	2.88	14.34	52.60	-25.47
303	3.11	2.80			-26.05
308	3.19	2.74			-26.55
313	3.24	2.68			-27.03

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The interaction of IH extract with HSA α 1,2-AMy supports its potential as an effective natural therapeutic agent that can provide a more sustainable effect on starch metabolism compared to conventional inhibitors for diabetes management. By inhibiting this enzyme, IH promote improved glycemic control while also offering antioxidant and anti-inflammatory benefits.

Early indications have indicated that the ethanolic extract of the IH has low phytotoxicity even at low and middle concentrations demonstrating its safety to undergo further pharmacological analysis. However, complete profiling of the toxicology including cytotoxicity and acute toxicity would be crucial to determine its safety margin. As a support of its antidiabetic potential, future research should also involve cell-based glucose uptake, and rodent oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) to confirm its in vitro enzyme inhibitory features under physiological conditions. These measures will assist in confirming the efficacy and bioavailability of the extract as well as the systemic safety hence further development of the extract as a potential alternative natural therapeutic in diabetes management.

REFERENCES

- Afroz Shoily, M. S., Islam, M. E., Rasel, N. M., Parvin, S., Barmon, J., Hasan Aqib, A. & Parvin, M. S. (2025). Unveiling the biological activities of *Heliotropium indicum* L. plant extracts: anti-inflammatory activities, GC–MS analysis, and in-silico molecular docking. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1), 3285.
- Alqahtani, A. S., Hidayathulla, S., Rehman, M. T., ElGamal, A. A., Al-Massarani, S., Razmovski-Naumovski, V., Alqahtani, M.S., El Dib, R.A. and AlAjmi, M. F. (2019). Alpha-amylase and alpha-glucosidase enzyme inhibition and antioxidant potential of 3-oxolupenal and katononic acid isolated from *Nuxia oppositifolia*. *Biomolecules*, 10(1), 61.
- Braca, A.; De Tommasi, N.; Di Bari, L.; Pizza, C.; Politi, M.; Morelli, I. (2001). Antioxidant principles from *Bauhinia tarapotensis*. *Journal of Natural Product*, 64, 892–895.
- Bradford, M.M. (1976). A rapid and sensitive method for the quantitation of microgram quantities of protein utilizing the principle of protein–dye binding. *Analytical Biochemistry*. 38; 248–254.
- Deng, F.Y. and Liu, Y. (2012). Study of the interaction between tosofloxacin tosylate and bovine serum albumin by multi-spectroscopic methods. *Journal of Luminescence*, 132(2): 443-448.
- Edeoga, H. O., Okwu, D. E., & Mbaebie, B. O. (2005). Phytochemical constituents of some Nigerian medicinal plants. *African journal of biotechnology*, 4(7), 685-688.
- Falese, B. A., Kolawole, A. N., Sarumi, O. A., & Kolawole, A. O. (2021). Probing the interaction of iminium form of sanguinarine with human salivary α -amylase by multi-spectroscopic techniques and molecular docking. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 334, 116346.
- Kaurinovic, B., & Vastag, D. (2019). Flavonoids and phenolic acids as potential natural antioxidants. *Antioxidants*, 2(1), 1-14.
- Khursheed, R., Singh, S.K., Wadhwa, S., Kapoor, B., Gulati, M., Kumar, R., Ramanunny, A.K., Awasthi, A. and Dua, K. (2019). Treatment strategies against diabetes: Success so far and challenges ahead. *European journal of pharmacology*, 862, p.172625.
- Kolawole, A.N., Akinladejo, V.T., Elekofehinti, O.O., Akinmoladun, A.C., Kolawole (2018). Experimental and computational modeling of interaction of kolaviron-kolaflavanone with aldehyde dehydrogenase. *Bioorganic Chemistry*, 78; 68–79.
- Padhi, S., Nayak, A. K., & Behera, A. (2020). Type II diabetes mellitus: a review on recent drug based therapeutics. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 131, 110708.
- Pahuja, S., Garg, M., Kumari, T., Bhatia, S., & Sarup, P. (2022). Compendious review on bioactive constituents and Pharmacotherapeutic profile of *Heliotropium indicum* Linn. *The Natural Products Journal*, 12(1), 38-53.
- Pahuja, S., Garg, M., Kumari, T., Bhatia, S., & Sarup, P. (2022). Compendious review on bioactive constituents and Pharmacotherapeutic profile of *Heliotropium indicum* Linn. *The Natural Products Journal*, 12(1), 38-53.

- Pesaresi, A. (2023). Mixed and non-competitive enzyme inhibition: underlying mechanisms and mechanistic irrelevance of the formal two-site model. *Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry*, 38(1), 2245168.
- Ravathy, S., Elumalai, S., Benny, M. and Antony, B. (2011). Isolation, Purification and Identification of Curcuminoids from Tumeric (*Curcuma longa*) by Column Chromatography. *Journal of Experimental Sciences*; 2(7); 21-25.
- Visvanathan, R., Qader, M., Jayathilake, C., Jayawardana, B. C., Liyanage, R., & Sivakanesan, R. (2020). Critical review on conventional spectroscopic α -amylase activity detection methods: merits, demerits, and future prospects. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 100(7), 2836-2847.